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SWRI
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External Scientific Report

PPP exposure models for 3D orchards considering spraying technologies in Southern Europe

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Appendix A – National statistical data

A.1. Original data from Greece

Regions	Orange	Mandarin	Lemon	Apricot	Cherry	Peach - Nectarine	Vines for wine	Olive trees	Almond	Walnut	Chestnut	Hazelnut & pistachio	Vines for table grapes	Vines for raisins
	Surface (ha)													
Greece Total	29.451	8.179	4.102	8.102	15.736	39.404	49.504	793.092	15.207	13.881	8.873	5.471	9.886	27.624
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	0	0	0	189	658	225	2.257	14.899	1.213	1.141	53,8	61	2.852	0,2
Central Macedonia	2	1	1	4.266	12.482	33.667	4.144	40.043	3.629	2.220	2.098,5	488	1.871	14
Western Macedonia	0	0	0	31	759	2.220	1.577	321	860	1.523	367	95	164	
Epirus	3.159	2.875	143	16	13	28	735	19.378	48	338	169,5	52	11	0,1
Thessally	9	5	6	744	933	2.495	3.938	26.815	7.716	3.253	2.802	1.321	1.219	1,1
Central Greece	101	16	44	30	339	129	5.470	80.655	880	1.877	382,5	2.399	121	29
Ionian Islands	82	25	70	5	5	5	1.670	33.707	41	16			22	1.158
Western Greece	5.568	858	1.997	28	130	46	5.260	83.272	262	700	242	14	164	7.064
Peloponnese	16.910	3.473	1.110	2.731	347	481	7.552	220.704	330	2.535	1.585	38	696	10.477
Attica	42	19	141	4	6	3	5.745	15.810	43	8	0,5	949	53	
Northern Aegean	358	299	86	9	29	7	2.205	53.037	127	26	928	0,2	127	
Southern Aegean	289	145	120	18	3	67	2.929	14.784	35	4	0,4	43	132	0,1
Crete	2.931	464	384	31	34	32	6.023	189.666	22,1	241	244	12	2.454	8.881

3D-orchards – Appendix A

A.2. Original data from Italy

Regions	Oranges	Lemons	Apricot	Cherry	Wine grapes	Table grapes	Table and oil olives	Peach	Nectarine	Almond	Hazelnut	Pistachio	Clementine	Tangerine
	Surface (ha)													
Italy	82729	25812	20089	30011	669827	47416	1164568	42835	19267	53076	86725	3922	25762	8594
Piemonte			706	353	42961	206	132	1609	2119		24557			
Lombardia		1	103	189	24962		2394	317	84	5	259			
Veneto			390	2105	89288	69	5160	1333	736	1	540			
Liguria	16	27	65	24	1624	2	16840	109	6		27		3	7
Trentino Alto Adige / Südtirol			94	389	15763	91	392	5	2		4			
Friuli-Venezia Giulia			10	24	24052		625	162	14		11			
Emilia-Romagna			6303	2142	53385	26	4155	4267	6802	7	141			
Toscana	4	3	191	146	59213	70	89929	476	119	63	468		2	
Lazio	420	64	147	860	20347	984	82931	1675	315	35	24578		88	22
Campania	990	1235	4757	3181	25633	69	75763	15551	4134	13	21452	35	283	438
Puglia	3890	283	1155	18709	88109	24985	384300	3250	860	19825	10	1	4995	128
Calabria	16382	1019	626	386	8831	328	184529	1739	1083	187	304		16097	2412
Sicilia	54964	23009	996	744	120262	18776	157891	6254	916	31618	13808	3881	2225	4731
Sardegna	2215	121	138	289	26619	561	40604	1547	175	1023	147		793	200
Umbria			24	20	12300	11	27001	116	22	5	144			
Marche			180	84	15859	16	9606	534	253	16	21			
Abruzzo	6		299	182	32529	673	41895	1819	521	137	132			
Molise	8	1	140	8	5593	60	14335	210	95	60	75		1	
Basilicata	3834	49	3765	176	2027	489	26086	1862	1011	81	45	5	1275	656
Valle d'Aosta / Vallée d'Aoste					470						2			

A.3. Original data from Spain

Region	Orange	Mandarin	Lemon	Apricot	Cherry	Peach & nectarine	Kiwi	Nuts (almond, walnut, hazelnut, chestnut, pistachio)	Wine grape	Table & raisin grape	Oil & table olive	Table olive	Oil olive
SURFACE (ha)													
Spain total	139.971	105.583	46.684	20.235	27.604	77.464	1.549	788.266	920.525	16.363	2.601.901	166.774	2.435.127
Andalucía	57.509	19.971	6.539	518	1.893	4.646	12	226.810	25.627	3.068	1.633.215	94.952	1.538.263
Aragón	-	-	-	2.659	8.962	20.475	56	79.172	34.833	181	46.534	-	46.534
C. Valenciana	70.344	73.068	13.778	3.766	2.678	4.417	143	94.960	58.688	5.463	93.741	465	93.276
Cantabria	-	-	8	-	1	1	7	10	119	-	-	-	-
Castilla la Mancha	-	-	-	1.559	278	2.264	-	164.786	441.357	66	373.849	230	373.619
Castilla y León	3	-	-	2	1.595	54	-	5.879	82.074	9	8.150	549	7.601
Cataluña	2.188	6.536	30	1.862	2.775	20.880	36	52.621	56.594	18	109.731	416	109.315
Extremadura	51	7	1	653	7.524	8.567	16	16.228	78.683	299	264.286	68.954	195.332
Galicia	84	-	192	88	678	1.015	837	25.412	24.134	-	275	-	275
Islas Baleares	1.677	261	185	425	29	148	12	24.043	2.237	50	8.524	108	8.416
Islas Canarias	952	97	260	67	5	138	9	245	6.244	91	425	97	328
La Rioja	-	-	-	30	456	483	5	10.472	47.447	4	5.651	-	5.651
Madrid	-	-	-	1	2	1	34	2.038	8.197	-	26.696	111	26.585
Navarra	-	-	-	17	339	471	25	4.257	17.950	-	7.752	-	7.752
P. de Asturias	-	-	-	-	-	-	246	-	114	-	-	-	-
País Vasco	-	-	1	-	16	13	111	357	14.143	-	365	-	365
R. de Murcia	7.161	5.643	25.690	8.588	373	13.891	-	80.976	22.084	7.114	22.707	892	21.815